

Disturbance Observer-Based Predictive Functional Critical Control of a Table Drive System

Authors : Toshiyuki Satoh, Hiroki Hara, Naoki Saito, Jun-ya Nagase, Norihiko Saga

Abstract : This paper addresses a control system design for a table drive system based on the disturbance observer (DOB)-based predictive functional critical control (PFCC). To empower the previously developed DOB-based PFC to handle constraints on controlled outputs, we propose to take a critical control approach. To this end, we derive the transfer function representation of the PFC controller, and yield a detailed design procedure. The effectiveness of the proposed method is confirmed through an experimental evaluation.

Keywords : critical control, disturbance observer, mechatronics, motion control, predictive functional control, table drive systems

Conference Title : ICAM 2014 : International Conference on Automation and Mechatronics

Conference Location : Melbourne, Australia

Conference Dates : December 16-17, 2014